

Synthesis and Physiological Activity of 3-Hydroxyphenyl 5-Aryl Isoxazoles

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A few 3-*o*- and 3-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-5-aryl isoxazoles have been synthesized for elucidating the antibacterial and antifungal properties, starting from appropriately substituted chalconedibromides and subsequent treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The tests revealed that 3-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-5-*p*-chlorophenyl isoxazole possesses the maximum activity against both bacteria and fungi.

A NUMBER of heterocycles substituted with hydroxyphenyl moieties are used as analgesic¹, antitissive² and anticonvulsant³ drugs. They also possess high hypnotic³ and anthelmintic⁵ activities. A detailed survey of literature revealed that very few hydroxyaryl substituted isoxazoles have so far been reported. Except for two instances^{6,7}, where the chalconedibromide method was utilized for making them, the method of preparation reported involved either the treatment of a hydroxy substituted β -diketone with hydroxylamine⁶ or conversion of a chromone derivative into the hydroxyaryl isoxazole with the same reagent⁸. No spectral study or physiological activity evaluation has been carried out in any one of these earlier reports. Hence, the synthesis of a few hydroxyaryl isoxazoles has been undertaken with a view to obtain spectral data and ascertain the physiological activity of the compounds synthesised.

o- and *p*-Hydroxy acetophenones have been condensed with various aromatic aldehydes to get the chalcones (I, chart I), which have then been converted into the isoxazoles (III) by adopting the procedure of Wheeler and associates⁶. The isoxazoles synthesised, together with their mps, analytical data and antibacterial and antifungal properties are listed in Table I.

Spectra: The spectral characteristics of a few these compounds have already been discussed in an earlier communication⁹. The isoxazoles reported in the present investigation exhibited the same behaviour. All the isoxazoles showed absorptions in ir at 1620, 1570-1550, 1450 ± 15 , 1300-1250, 1070 and

1140 ± 10 cm^{-1} characteristic of isoxazole ring system and are analogous to the data reported earlier by Katritzky and coworkers¹⁰. 3-*p*-Hydroxyphenyl-5-aryl isoxazoles absorb at 3600 cm^{-1} in the hydroxy region, whereas the 3-*o*-hydroxyphenyl compounds exhibited band at 3200 cm^{-1} indicative of strong chelation between OH and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ in the latter.

Bacteriostatic activity: Bacteriostatic activity has been evaluated by adopting the tube dilution method¹¹ and three representative bacteria, viz., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* were employed as test organisms of the sixteen compounds tested, 3-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-5-*p*-chlorophenyl isoxazole has been found to be the most active and inhibited the growth of all the three bacterial species employed at 2 ppm. 3-Phenyl-5-*p*-hydroxyphenyl isoxazole, which has been found to be active to *Staphylococcus aureus* even at 2 ppm., was inactive to the other two species of bacteria even at 100 ppm. 3-*p*-Hydroxy phenyl-5-*p*-methoxy phenyl and 3-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-5-*o*-chlorophenyl isoxazoles have been active only to *Bacillus subtilis* at 2 ppm., whereas against the other species the activity has been found only at 100 ppm.

Fungistatic activity: The fungistatic activity has been assessed by the radial growth measurement technique¹² and *Aspergillus niger* has been the test organism made use of. In the case of fungistatic testing, also, the maximum activity was shown by 3-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-5-*p*-chlorophenyl isoxazole. Its percentage inhibition has been found to be 90 and 70 at 100 and 10 ppm. respectively. This was followed in order by 3-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-5-*p*-chlorophenyl isoxazole whose percentage inhibition has been 80 and 50 at 100 and 10 ppm. respectively.

Experimental

General procedures for the preparation of isoxazoles:

(i) **Chalcone:** The appropriate aldehyde and ketone were mixed in equimolar proportions in alcohol solution and treated with sodium hydroxide (30%

TABLE I—ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTIFUNGAL PROPERTIES OF 3-HYDROXYPHENYL-5-ARYLISOXAZOLES

ISOXAZOLE		MP (°C)	% Nitrogen		Bacteriostatic activity			Fungistatic activity (%) inhibition (AN)	
3-Substituent	5-Substituent		Calcd.	Found	EC A B	BS A B	SA A B	A	B
* <i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	210	—	—	-+	--	++	45	15
* <i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	198	—	—	-±	++	-+	30	10
* <i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	255	—	—	++	-±	++	35	10
* <i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	210	—	—	++	-±	++	40	10
* <i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	198	—	—	-±	-+	++	30	5
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	235	5.2	5.3	-±	-±	-±	80	50
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	209	10.0	10.1	-+	++	±±	35	5
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Piperonyl	253	5.0	5.0	-±	++	±±	45	10
* <i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	225	—	—	++	±±	-±	50	25
* <i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	198	—	—	-+	--	-+	40	5
* <i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	255	—	—	-+	±±	±-	35	5
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	233	5.2	5.3	--	--	--	90	60
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Piperonyl	217	5.0	4.9	±±	++	±±	50	10
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	2 : 4-Dichlorophenyl	300	4.5	4.4	-±	-±	±±	50	20
* <i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	185	—	—	-+	-±	++	40	5
* Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	165	—	—	++	-+	--	60	35

* Compounds earlier reported by us (see reference no. 9).

† The compounds gave satisfactory carbon and hydrogen analysis.

A = 100 ppm.

B = 10 ppm.

- = no growth

± = partial growth

+ = full growth

EC = *Escherichia coli*

BS = *Bacillus subtilis*

SA = *Staphylococcus aureus*

AN = *Aspergillus niger*.

aqueous). The mixture was maintained at 60° on a water bath for about three hours and the chalcone isolated by acidification. Recrystallization was effected from alcohol.

(ii) *Dibromide*: The chalcone (0.01 mole) in ether or carbon disulphide was treated with bromine solution (0.01 mole) in the same solvent with stirring over a period of 10 min at 5°. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with a little cold ether and recrystallized from alcohol. The following dibromides have been reported for the first time.

1. 4-Chloro-2'-hydroxychalconedibromide. mp. 185° (Calc. for C, 41.0; H, 2.6; found C, 40.9; H, 2.7%).

2. 4-Dimethylamino-2'-hydroxychalconedibromide m.p. 149°. (Calc. for N, 3.3; found N, 3.4%).

3. 3, 4-Methylenedioxy-2'-hydroxychalconedibromide. mp. 130°. (Calc. for C, 44.0; H, 2.8; found 44.3; H, 2.9%).

4. 4-Chloro-4'-hydroxychalconedibromide. mp. 215°. (Calc. for C, 41.0; H, 2.6; found C, 41.2; H, 2.6%).

5. 3, 4-Methylenedioxy-4'-hydroxychalconedibromide. m.p. 190°. (Calc. for C, 44.6; H, 2.8; found C, 44.5; H, 2.9%).

6. 2,4-Dichloro-4-hydroxychalconedibromide. mp. 193°. (Calc. for C, 39.6; H, 2.2; found C, 39.5; H, 2.3%).

(iii) *Isoxazoles*: The dibromide (0.01 mole) was dissolved by boiling in alcohol and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mole aqueous solution) was

added followed by potassium hydroxide (30% aqueous). The mixture was allowed to stand for about 10 min and the isoxazole isolated by acidification.

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